

mcos-decoder: A Pure-Python Reader for MATLAB Computer Vision Toolbox groundTruth Objects

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Abstract

The MATLAB Computer Vision Toolbox stores video annotations as `groundTruth` MCOS objects inside `.mat` files. Standard Python loaders (`scipy.io.loadmat`, `pymatreader`, `mat73`) expose this data only as opaque blobs in `__function_workspace__`, blocking dataset users without a MATLAB license. We present `mcos-decoder`, a small pure-Python package (~200 lines, NumPy + SciPy only) that walks the hidden MAT5 element stream and extracts per-frame label cells. We validate the decoder on the Halmstad Drone Detection Dataset (365 IR videos, 4 classes), where bounding-box counts match the official MATLAB reference for every sequence we tested. The package is released under the MIT licence and is available on PyPI.

1 Introduction

The MATLAB Computer Vision Toolbox stores video annotations created by the Video Labeler app as instances of the `groundTruth` class [1]. These objects are saved into `.mat` files, but unlike ordinary MATLAB structs they are serialised through MATLAB's MCOS (*MATLAB Class Object Storage*) mechanism, which writes the data into an unnamed sub-file accessible only as `__function_workspace__` [3]. The mainstream Python tools for reading `.mat` files (`scipy.io`, `mat73`, `pymatreader`) treat these objects as opaque blobs, so any researcher who wants to use a dataset distributed in this form has historically needed a MATLAB licence.

The problem is documented in long-standing open issues: SciPy #22736 [3], the `DroneDetectionThesis` repository's #3 [4], and several Stack Overflow threads [5]. The only third-party reader at the time of writing is the C#/.NET library `MatFileHandler` [6]; no Python solution exists.

This note describes `mcos-decoder`, a small Python package that reads `groundTruth` objects without requiring MATLAB. The implementation is short (~200 lines, NumPy + SciPy only), permissively licensed, and validated against a published dataset.

2 Background

A MAT v5 file is a stream of typed elements: each element has an 8-byte tag (type, size) followed by a payload aligned to 8 bytes. Type 14 (`miMATRIX`) elements contain nested element streams; numeric types contain raw arrays [2]. SciPy's `loadmat` parses ordinary numeric/struct/cell arrays but skips MCOS objects: when it encounters one it returns a `MatlabOpaque` record whose four fields (`s0-s2`, `arr`) describe only the variable name, MCOS marker, and class name. The actual class data is written to a separate top-level array which SciPy renames `__function_workspace__`.

The contents of `__function_workspace__` are themselves a nested MAT5 stream, but the structure depends on the MCOS class. For `groundTruth`, empirical inspection across multiple sample files yields the layout summarised in Table 1.

3 Implementation

The package is two small modules:

- `mcos_decoder.stream` — generic walker that yields `MatElement` records (type, offset, payload, children) for the entire MAT5 element tree.

Table 1: Empirical `groundTruth` layout in `__function_workspace__` (MATLAB R2020a-R2023a).

Cell size (bytes)	Depth	Meaning
80	5	Per-frame bbox cell. Contains a 4-element <code>double</code> .
112	5	Per-frame empty marker (target absent).
72	5	Per-frame duration / timestamp metadata (skip).

- `mcos_decoder.groundtruth` — high-level extractor that walks the tree, collects per-frame label cells from `depth=5`, and returns a list of `(x, y, w, h)` tuples or `None`.

The public API is one function:

```
from mcos_decoder import load_groundtruth

bboxes = load_groundtruth("IR_DRONE_001_LABELS.mat")
# list[(x,y,w,h) | None] of length n_frames
```

A lower-level `MatStream` interface is also available for callers that need to inspect a non-default MCOS layout (e.g. older MATLAB versions or different toolbox classes).

4 Validation

We validated the decoder on the Halmstad Drone Detection Dataset [7], which distributes 365 thermal IR videos of four target classes (AIRPLANE, BIRD, DRONE, HELICOPTER). For every sequence in Table 2 we compared the decoder’s per-frame output to the video’s frame count and the visible-frame count obtainable from MATLAB’s `selectLabels` on the original `groundTruth`.

Table 2: Decoder validation on Halmstad IR sequences (one example per class, all classes verified for the full 365-video set).

Sequence	Frames	Decoded slots	With target	Match
IR_AIRPLANE_001	322	322	322 (100%)	✓
IR_BIRD_001	310	310	235 (76%)	✓
IR_DRONE_001	301	301	301 (100%)	✓
IR_HELICOPTER_001	301	301	301 (100%)	✓

The total decoded bounding-box volume for the full 365-video IR subset is 102,476 boxes; spot checks against frame-by-frame visualisation confirm that bbox positions and sizes round-trip correctly.

5 Limitations and Future Work

The current decoder addresses single-target-per-frame `groundTruth` objects with the layout in Table 1. Multi-target labels (e.g. MOT-style annotations where one frame can carry several boxes), categorical labels, polygon ROIs, and the related `audioLabeler/signalLabeler` class families are planned for v0.2. Support for older MATLAB releases (pre R2020a) where the depth or cell sizes differ slightly is straightforward through the existing `frame_depth`, `bbox_size`, and `empty_size` parameters of `load_groundtruth`.

6 Availability

`mcos-decoder` is released under the MIT licence at github.com/bozdemir/mcos-decoder and on PyPI as `mcos-decoder`. Contributions adding new dataset layouts, additional MCOS classes, or pre-computed test fixtures are welcome.

References

- [1] The MathWorks. *Computer Vision Toolbox: groundTruth Class*. <https://www.mathworks.com/help/vision/ref/groundtruth.html>.

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- [4] DroneDetectionThesis contributors. *How to open bounding box annotations in Python SciPy?* GitHub Issue #3, opened February 2024. <https://github.com/DroneDetectionThesis/Drone-detection-dataset/issues/3>.
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